

tested to determine drought tolerance.

Seeds of each variety were drilled in rainfed fields on 31 Mar 1983 in 5-m-long rows in 3 replications. Stand establishment, drought damage, drought recovery ability, and phenotypic acceptability were recorded 21, 45, 81, and 133 days after seeding (DS). From 21 to 45 DS the plot received 7 mm precipitation. Maximum air and soil temperature ranged from 31.6 to 41.3°C and 34.7 to 48.3°C.

Twenty entries had a drought score of 9 at 45 DS. Eleven entries, including the susceptible check, died during the vegetative period. Pureline selection NC487/77 and hybrid lines CN506-147-2-1 and CN506-147-14-2 (IR30/LMN111//IR1514A-E660) performed better than the resistant check. Jalaplaba, Jaladhi 2, Jaladhi 3, and Janki, all pureline selections, had a high level of drought tolerance (see table). □

TABLE CONTINUED

Entry	Initial stand establishment, 21 DS	Drought tolerance, 45 DS	Recovery, 81 DS	Height (cm), 133 DS	Phenotypic acceptability 133 DS
NC488/78	3.6	6.3	5	71.4	4.3
Achra 108/1	3.6	5	3.6	77.5	3.6
Jalaplaba	2.3	2.3	3	77.8	2.6
FR13A	5.6	7	6.3	63.8	6.3
Jaladhi 1	6.3	6.3	5	75.9	5.6
Jaladhi 2	4.3	3.6	3	83.2	3
Jaladhi 3	3	1.6	3	95.8	2.6
Janki (C64-117)	3	1.6	3	87.5	2.6
Tilokkachari	6.3	6.3	7	74.5	6.3
<i>New varieties</i>					
CN506-147-2-1	3	3	2.3	83.3	2.3
CN506-147-14-2	3	5	3	52.8	2.3
CN683-1	5.6	5	5	80.5	3.6
FPAR 7809	5.6	5	4.3	50.1	5
<i>Resistant check</i>					
Dular	5	3.6	3	102.5	2.6
Salumpikit	8.3	9	8.3	58.7	8.3
<i>Susceptible check</i>					
IR20	9	9	9	28.5	9
Rainfall (mm)	105.9	7.0	116.1		210.5

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Three replications. DS = days after sowing.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Plant height and growth duration at increased water depths

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Popular semidwarfs were compared with tall varieties in duration and plant height at 55 and 74 cm water depths. Thirty-

day-old seedlings were transplanted during the last week of June. Nitrogen was applied in 2 equal splits to supply 40 kg N/ha during tillering stage. Plots were flooded 45 days after planting and water level was maintained for 3 months, until the first week of November.

Semidwarfs generally showed greater increase in plant height (28-36 cm) than

intermediate and tall (18-34 cm) varieties. MTU16, the traditional deepwater variety, increased 16 cm at 55-cm depth, and 40 cm at 75-cm depth. Flowering duration was delayed by 4-13 days for semidwarfs and 0-8 days for intermediate and tall varieties. Semidwarf varieties had weak stems and lodged at the 75-cm water depth. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Himalaya 1 and Himalaya 2 — two new semidwarf, cold-tolerant rices for Himachal Pradesh, India

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Fifty percent of the rice area of Himachal Pradesh is at altitudes higher than 900 m.

Cold temperatures during flowering reduce rice yields.

Himalaya 1 and Himalaya 2, semidwarf indicas released in 1982, can be successfully cultivated up to 1,550 m altitudes. Himalaya 1, the experimental line HPU734, is a very early maturing selection from IR579 (IR8/Tadukan). It is recommended for low, mid, and high hills. Himalaya 2, the experimental line

HPU71, is an early maturing selection from Pusa 33 (Improved sabarmati/Ratna). It is recommended for low and mid hills up to 1,300 m.

Himalaya 1 is high yielding, cold tolerant, and blast resistant. It yields an average 3.9 t/ha — 26, 15, and 3% more than IR579, China 988, or Himdhan (Table 1). It has long, slender, translucent grains with good cooking quality.

Himalaya 2 is high yielding, blast resistant, and early maturing. It yields 3.5 t/ha and has scented, long, bold grains which cook sticky, if used without previous storage. Other varietal characteristics are described in Table 2.

Yield stability data for 20 rices

tested in 9 environments at different elevations in 1977 and 1978 show Himalaya 1 had high yield and high stability (regression 1.10 and regression deviation 0.56). Himalaya 2 had average yield and high stability (regression 1.02 and regression deviation 0.09).

In 1980 minikit trials in farmer's fields, both varieties averaged 3.6 t/ha and outyielded local checks by 44%. Highest yields recorded were 7.7 t/ha for Himalaya 1 and 6.3 t/ha for Himalaya 2. □

Table 1. Grain yield of Himalaya 1 and Himalaya 2 in Himachal Pradesh hills, India. ^a

Year	Himalaya 1	IR579	China 988	Himdhan	Himalaya 2	IR579	China 988	Himdhan
	<i>Grain yield (t/ha)</i>							
1976	—	—	—	—	3.9 (4)	3.3 (4)	—	3.5 (4)
1977	4.7 (6)	3.8 (6)	4.0 (6)	4.8 (6)	3.1 (3)	2.8 (3)	3.3 (3)	3.3 (3)
1978	3.9 (11)	3.5 (11)	3.6 (11)	4.2 (11)	3.6 (11)	3.5 (11)	3.6 (11)	4.2 (11)
1979	4.0 (10)	2.2 (10)	3.4 (10)	3.5 (10)	3.3 (10)	2.2 (10)	3.4 (10)	3.5 (10)
1980	3.3 (15)	2.8 (4)	2.6 (6)	2.7 (11)	3.1 (4)	2.8 (4)	—	—
Mean	3.9 (42)	3.1 (31)	3.4 (33)	3.8 (38)	3.5 (32)	2.9 (32)	3.4 (24)	3.6 (28)
	<i>Increase over respective checks (%)</i>							
		26	15	3	—	21	3	—3

^a Values in parentheses indicate the number of locations for which yields were averaged.

Table 2. Agronomic and quality characteristics of Himalaya 1 and Himalaya 2.

	Himalaya 1	Himalaya 2	IR579	China 988	Himdhan
Plant height (cm)	65	74	68	102	99
Days to maturity	125	130	140	128	130
Panicles (no./m ²)	254	226	258	245	207
Spikelets/panicle	111	110	111	79	117
Sterility (76)	12.4	19.3	18.1	15.6	18.0
1,000-grain wt (g)	24.8	25.5	20.6	24.3	25.3
Protein (%)	5.7	7.7	8.0	6.3	7.6
Amylose (%)	24.7	20.3	21.7	21.0	22.9
Alkali digestion value (1-7 scale)	6.2	6.7	6.9	6.3	7.0
Grain shape	Long slender	Long bold	Long slender	Medium bold	Medium bold
Blast, leaf (0-9 scale)	3.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	4.5
Blast, neck (%)	5	5	5	25	10

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Tissue culture

Anther culture in rice

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Anther culture techniques can shorten the time required to develop a rice variety and may cost less to use than conventional breeding methods. Tamil Nadu Agricultural University initiated anther culture studies in 1980.

F₁ and F₂ of crosses ASD8/Vaigai, ASD8/Amaravathi, ASD8/Bagavathi, and

ASD8/Zhinjan responded to anther culture by producing calluses after 35 to 42 days of incubation in darkness at 24-26°C (Table 1).

Potato extract medium and N6 medium supplemented with 2 mg 2,4-D/liter were used. Anther response in callus production varied from 2 to 10% and was best in N6 medium. Anther response of ASD8/Bagavathi was best (9.51%). ASD8/Zhinjan had minimum response (2.38%) (Table 1).

Table 1. Anther response of selected Tamil Nadu Agricultural University rices, 1980.

Medium	Cross	Anthers inoculated (no.)	Anther response		Av time for response (days)
			no.	%	
N6	ASD8/Vaigai (F ₁)	540	22	4.07	42
Potato extract	- do -	460	18	3.91	40
N6	ASD8/Amaravathi (F ₁)	648	47	7.25	40
Potato extract	- do -	505	25	4.95	42
N6	ASD8/Bagavathi (F ₂)	536	51	9.51	35
Potato extract	- do -	485	39	8.04	38
N6	ASD8/Zhinjan (F ₁)	443	14	3.16	38
Potato extract	- do -	420	10	2.38	40